

Women Entrepreneurship and Papad Industry

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Abstract: - Indian women are also called 'Annapurna', 'sugaran', 'Ruchira'. This Annapurna really takes care of the whole family. Caring for the preferences of each person in the family. Makes fresh and various type of food for family members. 'Papad' is one such food found in every Indian households. In today's fast paced world it is not possible for every women to make papad at home. Therefore, such women tend to buy ready-made papad. There is a huge demand for papad from caterers, hoteliers, shopkeepers, retailers, women who leave home for work. Some women feel that they are selling papad to help their family, while some women seem to be making papad from other and selling it in the market. From this, it seems that papad industry has been established. This research paper gives a brief overview of some of the women who have been successful in the papad industry in Dhule district. In this research success stories of women entrepreneurs whose making papad have been presented.

Keywords:-*Women, Entrepreneurship, Papad, Industry.*

Aims :-

- 1] To find out the women entrepreneurs who manufactured of papad.
- 2] To take record the success of women entrepreneurs who produce papad.

Hypothesis :-

The women of Dhule district have achieved success in the papad industry.

Settings:-

Women entrepreneurs who produce papad in Dhule District.

Design:-

Descriptive type of observational study.

Methods and Materials:-

Data were collected by interview of the women entrepreneurs engaged in this industry with a pre-designed and pre-tested schedule.

Conclusion

The women of Dhule district have achieved success in the papad industry.

In modern times, women are involved in every field like knowledge, science, space, research, politics, sociology, industry. Women have also made their debut in the formerly male dominated industry. It seems that, women have worked as entrepreneurs mainly in the fields of laundry, beauty salon, cottage industry, hotels, education and information technology. In the home based industry, it is felt that there are more women entrepreneurs. Also, women seem to have excelled as entrepreneurs of the 'Papad Industry'. In this research, the researcher has taken study of the success of women entrepreneurs in Dhule, who are entrepreneurs of 'Papad Industry'

The researcher feels the need to look at the definition of industry first in research.

1] The new encyclopedia Britannica

'An Industry is a group of company to produce an object to sell in market'.

2] Pro.EAG. Robinson:-

'An industry is a group of firms producing and distributing similar products and services'.

*Agro-Base Industries :-

-Dr. V. B. Kondawar

'The agro-based industry is the industry that processes the products that come out of agricultural inputs'.

From the above definition of agro-based industry, it is evident that agriculture produces Rice, wheat, maize, Millet, sugarcane, Sunflower, Groundnut, Sesame, lentil, lentils, Soyabean, Nachani, Mustard etc. There are many industries that use and process these agricultural product. 'Papad Industry' is one of them. Many women in India seem to have helped their families financially through the papad industry. Many women from Dhule district work as entrepreneurs in this papad industry.

Women Entrepreneur:-

"A small scale industrial unit, industry related service or business enterprise, managed by one or more women entrepreneurs in proprietary concerns, or in which she / they individually or jointly, have share capital of not less than 51 percent as partners / shareholders / director of private limited company / members of co-operation society, is defined as a women enterprise".

Women Entrepreneur in Dhule District who produce 'papad'.

1] Renuka Lakhichand Chavan

Renuka lakhichand Chavan lives in 'Patalde' village in Dhule. Renuka and some women from her village make papad and sell it. Before the establishment of this industry, Renuka's financial situation was very poor. She did not have even her own house to live in. There was no money for Children's education. Her husband was not getting any job either. That's how Renuka saw a ray of hope from the 'papad' industry. With the help of MSRLM from Maharashtra, she set up a self help group with the help of women from the village and transformed her skills into papad industry. The business which started with the help of Rs. 8000 has now been transformed into a small scale industry. The annual turnover of Renuka's papad Industry has reached Rs.12 to 13 lakhs. Not only this, Renuka's own big house is also a godown for storing papad. During the seasons, Renuka and the women in her group work together to make up to 50kg of papad a day. Renuka's self-help group has received 'Rajmata Jijau Swavalamban Award' and 'Krishi Angrovan award.'

2] Sunita Prakash Mahajan:-

Sunita Prakash Mahajan from Dhule is in the business of making papad and also sells them 'Hat shevai'. Sunita learned the skill of making papads from her mother-in-law Meera Mahajan. The papad and Hat shevai made by Sunita are also bought by people from Dubai, Singapore and USA. The women members of the Annapurna savings group which she founded have a share of Rs 60,000 in the bank and an average annual turnover of Rs 11 lakhs from the home based industry.

3] Shubhangi Akesh Chhajed:-

Shubhangi Akesh Chhajed is a very famous entrepreneur from Dhule. She started 'Spark Food' papad industry in 2013. Her papad is known as 'Vimal Ashish papad'. The business started by Shubhangi's husband was transformed into a papad industry by Shubhangi. With an investment of Rs 30 lakh, it has an annual turnover of 70 lakh to 80 lakh. Vimal Ashish papad is located in Arvi, Dhadre, Dhule MIDC, Laling, Purmepada, Sadgoan area of Dhule. Vimal Ashish papad has 8 to 10 workers. Shubhangi Chhajed seems to be constantly emphasizing on expanding its entrepreneurial reach.

4] Swapnali Avinash Patil:-

Swapnali Avinash Patil is the resident of Shirpur. Swapnali invested Rs 15 lakhs and established Kamal Gruh Udyog in 2016. Swapnali was inspired by his family to set up a papad industry. Now this home industry has been

transformed into a micro-enterprise. Papad of Kamal Gruh Udyog is sold not only in Dhule but all over Maharashtra. 5 workers work in Swapnali's 'Kamal Gruh Udyog', is known to satisfactorily cater to the demand of its customer base. The business strives to make for a positive experience through its offerings. Customer centricity is at the core of Kamal Mahila Gruh Udyog in Shirpur and it is this belief that has led the business to build long term relationships.

5] Sangita Sanjay Yeole, Nardana

Sangita Sanjay Yeole is a very famous entrepreneur from Dhule. Sangita Sanjay Yeole started his own factory in Nardana MIDC in 2016 to produce 'papad' and other similar food item in M/S Kulsamini Industries. Sangita has invested over Rs 45 lakh in her papad industry. Her papad making factory has all the machines needed to make papad. About 10 workers work in this place to making and packaging of papad. Her papad is also sold outside of Maharashtra. Her aim is to sell papad from her factory in the country and abroad.

6] Vandana Lakshman Chaudhary:-

Vandana Lakshman Chaudhary is resident of Waghadi, Taluka Shindkheda. In the beginning Vandana used to roll the papad alone at home and sell it. When the order to make papad then used to make papad. She had profile by rolling papad alone, but it also took more time. The taste of papad spread everywhere and she started getting orders of 30-40 kg of papad per month, but this was not possible for Vandana alone. Then Vandana gathered 10 more women from the village and formed 'Jai Bhavani Self Help Group' for this she got a loan of Rs 5 lakhs from the bank. With the help of story of making papad. Each woman in the group earns an annual income of Rs 1 to 1.5 lakhs, from this business. This group of papad is in high demand from caterers and hoteliers. The aim of women in this group to transform this home used industry into a small scale industry soon.

7] Shweta Chetan Girase, Shirpur.

Shweta Chetan Girase is a resident of Shirpur. Entrepreneur Chetan Girase from Shirpur and his wife Shweta Chetan Girase founded 'Babaji Agro Industry' at Gartad. In her industry papad, appalam, and some other similar product are made. Shweta Chetan Girase started making papad in Babaji Agro Industry in 2019 with an investment of Rs. 50 lakhs. The factory employs about 25 workers. Shweta reached the pinnacle of success by succeeding in her entrepreneurship in a very short time.

Conclusion

From the information given in the relevant paper and other information, it is evident that in Dhule district also some women entrepreneurs have been success full in industries like papad. The women themselves have made great strides in the papad industry through their knowledge skills. In such a short span of time such entrepreneurial women have successes in creating financial independence place in society. Successful women entrepreneurs in such papad industry need to be published through the media so that the new generation of young women can be inspired by their entrepreneurship work ethic, risk taking ability , etc. Can inspired a new generation of young women and contribute to the economic development of the country by increasing overall entrepreneurship among women.

Suggestions:-

- 1] The women of Dhule District should look at the papad industry not only as a traditional industry but also look modernity to the papad industry.
- 2] To increase the participation of women in papad industry , it is necessary for the government to provide special encouragement to women in the industrial policy as well as in various schemes of the government and to Conway information related to trade and industrial management to women.
- 3] As there is a large amount of agricultural sector in Dhule District , a mechanism should be setup to provide guidance and information to women in agro-based papad industry and business.

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